

Diverse ion effect: The above titration was performed in presence of known amounts of foreign ions. The titrations were not hampered by the presence of a large number of foreign ions (mg): NH_4^+ (50), Na^+ (115), Ca^{2+} (25), Ba^{2+} (25), Al^{3+} (30), nitrate (120) and acetate (50). However, small amounts of Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , chloride, bromide and iodide seriously interfered.

References

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A New Potentiometric Method for the Sequential Titration of Permanganate and Vanadate with Sodium Oxalate at Room Temperature using Photochemical Reduction of Ferric Oxalate

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Experimental

STOCK solutions of vanadate, permanganate and sodium oxalate were prepared by the usual procedures¹.

A Philips high pressure mercury vapour lamp (Repro lamp) with a power consumption of 125 W was used for irradiating the titration mixture. A sensitive potentiometric setup consisting of a Toshniwal PL 52 portable potentiometer with a built in galvanometer was used in all potentiometric titrations. A bright platinum rod immersed in titration mixture and a saturated calomel half-cell were used as indicator and reference electrodes, respectively. The two cells are connected through a saturated ammonium nitrate solution salt-bridge.

Recommended procedure for the determination of permanganate and vanadate in mixtures: To different aliquots of 0.05 N permanganate or vana-

date or their mixtures solutions were added 0.05 M Fe^{III} solution (5.0 ml) and sufficient 20 N H_2SO_4 to keep the overall acidity at 1 N. The mixture was diluted with distilled water to 50 ml. The beaker was exposed under the light from a Repro lamp with its contents and then titrated with 0.05 M sodium oxalate solution potentiometrically keeping the overall titration period around 20 min under exposure to the light. The contents were stirred constantly with a magnetic stirrer. The variation in potentials of the system was followed for each aliquot of sodium oxalate added by potentiometric method.

Results and Discussion

When the solutions of permanganate and vanadate are individually titrated with sodium oxalate in presence of Fe^{III} , the Fe^{II} ions formed *in situ* due to the photochemical reduction of ferric oxalate is found to reduce Mn^{VII} to Mn^{II} and V^V to V^{IV} which can be followed potentiometrically. In this process, Fe^{III} is regenerated. The concentration of Fe^{III} is found to be not critical and if a minimum of Fe^{III} is maintained the titration can be effectively followed. However, in the complete absence of Fe^{III} the titrations can not be performed. Due to good differences in the redox potentials of $\text{Mn}^{VII}/\text{Mn}^{II}$ and V^V/V^{IV} systems from that of $\text{Fe}^{III}/\text{Fe}^{II}$ when all the oxidant is reduced completely, the indicator electrode responds to the later system resulting in large decrease in the potentials observed as end-point is reached.

The investigations revealed that these titrations can be best carried out in between 0.5 and 3.0 N acid medium with respect to sulphuric acid with 20 min time to complete the titration under exposure to light.

The same procedure can also be extended to titrate mixtures of permanganate and vanadate. In the titration of permanganate, vanadate mixtures with oxalate in presence of Fe^{III} variation in potentials of the system (Fig. 1) with increasing concentration of oxalate showed two breaks, the one corresponding to the complete reduction of permanganate (1 060–840 mV) and the second corresponding to the complete reduction of vanadate (980–530 mV).

To test the quantitative nature of the titrations of the mixtures of permanganate and vanadate, a large number of determinations are made with varying concentrations of permanganate and vanadate (in the range 0.05–0.30) which gave reproducible results with standard deviation in the range 0.003–0.005.

Reaction mechanism: When these oxidants are titrated with oxalate in presence of Fe^{III} under exposure to light, Fe^{III} will be preferentially reacting with oxalate added and may be undergoing

Fig. 1. Potentiometric determination of mixtures of permanganate and vanadate with oxalate under exposure to light in presence of Fe^{III}: (□) 2.0 ml of Mn^{VII} + 5.0 ml of V^V, (○) 5.0 ml of Mn^{VII} + 2.0 ml of V^V, and (×) 6.0 ml of Mn^{VII} + 5.0 ml of V^V.

photochemical reduction as proposed by Parker and Hatchard².

Thus this mechanism shows that each mole of oxalate produces two moles of CO₂ and Fe^{III}, and Fe^{II} produced in turn will reduce these oxidants. So for all practical purposes it can be considered as a titration of these oxidants with ferrous iron produced *in situ* which can be represented as

References

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